

THE RISE OF RADICAL DEMOCRACY: MODI'S AUTHORITARIANISM

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to critically examine the Democratic Political Process in India. The focus was to investigate the role of RSS in the decline of the parliamentary democratic system in India. An effort is made to understand, at first, the Democracy flourished in India, but it failed under Prime Minister Narendra Modi's government. Despite widespread insurgency, India managed to maintain its unity because of democratic considerations and asserts that they are the largest democracies in the world. To protect Hinduism and ban secularists, the Modi administration has manipulated the laws to crush dissent, abused the investigative process to pursue flimsy charges against political opponents. BJP vigilante groups like the RSS and the Bajrang Dal are speeding up India's conversion to a Hindu state.

At present, Modi is quite well-liked by Hindus. Since the start of his second term as Prime Minister of India in 2019, Narendra Modi has pursued policies that have weakened the nation's democracy. India is no longer a secular state, and the Hindutva movement has further polarized the already fractured nation. Not only are minorities living in India threatened by the BJP's annexation and expansion policies, but the neighboring nations are also concerned.

INTRODUCTION

All those legal actions that allow citizens to affect public policy are related to a political process. Democratization and the political system are related. Modern-day Democracy is traced back to the English Parliamentary Structure. The Greek words "demos," which means "the people," and "Kratos," which means "the rule," are combined to form the English word "democracy." Therefore, democracy refers to popular rule. Democracy is a form of government where the citizens elect the government through open, unrestricted elections. In a democracy, voters have a choice between various political parties and politicians competing for authority to govern. If representatives don't perform well, the public can criticize them and peacefully change them (Bhatti, 2005).

The Indian Constitution was drafted in 1947 with the principles of secularism, pluralism, religious tolerance, and equal citizenship. After Indonesia and Pakistan, India is the third-largest nation with 200 million Muslims. Jawaharlal Nehru proclaimed that all religions were permitted in India and that there was no official state religion. India has seen several state assembly elections as well as 16 closely contested general elections since 1952. Since the 1990s, panchayat or local elections have been successfully held in both urban and rural local governments.

India used to be regarded as the largest democracy in the world, but it now seems that this wonderful democracy is eroding. According to experts, this decrease started as soon as Narendra Modi and the

Bharatiya Janata Party assumed power. Modi and his party support Hindu nationalism and see India as the country of Hindus; they are affiliated with the extreme right. Muslims and Hindus have been at odds since Modi took office in 2014, and the violence has gotten worse every day (Ji, 2022).

Only those who consider India their homeland and Hinduism their faith is deserving of residing in this land, according to Vinayak Damodar Savarkar's 1923 book "Hindustva". He contended that although Muslims and Christians in India may satisfy the first need, they will never satisfy the second requirement because their sacred lands are the Arabian Peninsula and Palestine. The Bible and the Qurans, two of their sacred writings, are viewed as Hindu nationalists' credo (Mowlavi, 2023).

Significance of the Study

This study will help the reader to understand the importance of democratic government from economic, political, and social perspectives. It will provide a guideline to the readers to understand the weakness and causes of the failure of democracy in India and, on the other hand, for the rise of ethnic democracy in India.

Aims and objectives

The following are the main aims and objectives of the research.

1. The research aims to investigate the reasons for the rise of ethnic democracy in India.
2. To understand the RSS policies and impact on Indian Democracy.
3. The third objective of the paper is to understand how Modi's eight-year rule increased tension between religious groups, leading to sectarian wars.

Research questions

1. What are the main reasons at 75, India world's largest democracy turned into turmoil?
2. What is RSS, and its impact on policy formulation in India?
3. How do Modi's 2019's policies corrode the country's democracy?

Literature review

Jaffrelot and Schoch (2021) demonstrate in their book titled "Modi's India: Hindu Nationalism and the Rise of Ethnic Democracy" "how Modi's administration has led India towards an ethnic democracy that elevates the majority community above all others and reduces Muslims and Christians to second-class. A terrifying justification of how a widely supported leader has driven the largest democracy in the world towards authoritarianism and intolerance over the previous 20 years. Narendra Modi is the one who has driven this revolution. Attacks on intellectuals, colleges, NGOs, and secularists are the lifeblood of this imposing Hindu nationalism. Jaffrelot highlights the additional factors at play in the development of India's authoritarian political system. The government has centralized power at the expense of federalism and damaged institutions that were a part of the checks and balances in an effort to govern not just in New Delhi but also in the states. Modi's India is a dismal analysis of what has gone wrong with a once-vibrant democracy.

Patel (2022) is a columnist, essayist, and political expert who has long been a keen observer of the political landscape. He aims to clarify the statistics and information on India's success under Narendra Modi in his book entitled Price of the Modi Years.

Manmohan Singh, Modi's predecessor as prime minister, had previously predicted that Modi's tenure would be disastrous. This book approves. It acknowledges Modi's support; this is a description of the harm he has caused. India's recent political history includes an assessment of the harm done to the economy, national security, federalism, international relations, laws, judiciary, media, and civil society.

India represents the democratic recession on a global scale. The autocracy of the globe has been greatly influenced by India's recent downgrading to a mixed government. Furthermore, the pattern of India's democratic downfall shows how democracies today fall: not by a spectacular coup or the arrest of opposition leaders in the middle of the night, but rather by legalized opposition harassment, media intimidation, and the concentration of executive power (Tudor, 2023). The Narendra Modi administration is undermining the notion that

opposition is legitimate by associating criticism with the betrayal of the country. India is no longer the largest democracy in the world. However, observers of democracy concur that India currently exists in a transitional state between complete democracy and complete dictatorship. While groups that monitor democracies have varied classifications for democracies, they all identify India as a "hybrid regime" at this point in time, one that is neither fully autocratic nor fully democratic.

Muslims, who make up 14% of India's population, are treated worse now. According to a Human Rights Watch report from 2019, lynch mobs killed 44 people—36 of whom were Muslims—whom they believed were trading cows, owning meat, or eating it. Muslims have difficulty purchasing or leasing real estate, occasionally face denials of their requests to erect mosques, and are forbidden from publicly praying. Muslims are prohibited from praying at home by vigilantes. In one state, head coverings were prohibited for female Muslim students. Using garlands, a prominent member of Modi's Bharatiya Janata Party greeted convicted cow protectors. States under the BJP administration have enacted legislation to make it more difficult for interfaith weddings. The early release of eleven men convicted of raping a Muslim woman and killing some of her family members during the 2002 atrocities was welcomed by right-wing Hindus. Modi was the chief minister of Gujarat at the time of those incidents, and he was unable to put an end to Hindu violence against Muslims (Khanna & Shah, 2002). After that, Modi was denied entrance into the United States and the European Union until the Indian Supreme Court ruled that Modi had no case to answer. In India, a recent BBC documentary that accused Modi of collusion has been outlawed. Democratic assessment organizations have determined that India's record has gotten worse. India has been downgraded by Freedom House to "partly-free" status. India's democracy index dropped from 27 in 2014 to 46 in 2022.

Patronage democracy was a distinct type of democracy, with distinct voting patterns and, as a result, distinct conditions leading to ethnic party success. The Hindu nationalist Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), which has ruled India without interruption since 2014, is, without a doubt, the

most powerful party in the nation. The politics of religious polarization and fervent nationalism, along with Mr. Modi's charisma, are largely responsible for the BJP's electoral success. More than 80% of Indians are Hindu, and the BJP wants to bring them together and force them to vote as a single group (Chandra, 2013). The BJP, like other parties, has experienced internal strife. Its four decades in power represent a bare 12 percent of its total life in electoral politics. Being out of power meant that its workers would not receive patronage for an extended period of time.

The ideological roots of India's democratic decline can be traced back to the RSS, an organization that served as an opposing force to Gandhi's pro-independence Indian National Congress. Unlike the Congress, which supported secular liberal democracy, the RSS advocated for a future Indian nation defined solely by ethno-religious considerations – a "Hindu Rashtra" (Hindu nation). Its Hindutva ideology held that post-colonial India should be ruled by and for Hindus. "The foreign races in Hindusthan ... must lose their separate existence to merge in the Hindu race, or may stay in the country, wholly subordinated to the Hindu Nation, claiming nothing, deserving no privileges, far less any preferential treatment – not even citizen's rights (Basu, 2018b).

The country's 1949 constitution was written along secular-egalitarian lines, declaring that "the State shall not discriminate against any citizen solely on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth, or any combination of these". Meanwhile, the RSS had mostly succeeded in discrediting its political vision. Nathuram Godse, an RSS devotee, assassinated Mahatma Gandhi in 1948, a killing that Godse himself attributed to his Hindu nationalist ideology (Jha, 2023). The RSS was then banned for a year by the Indian government.

Modi has undermined Indian secularism and democracy through a mutually reinforcing cycle of two opposing agendas. The first is to use the premiership's powers to spread Hindutva ideology and divide the electorate along Hindu-versus-Muslim lines. The second is that he is consolidating power and weakening countervailing authorities such as the judiciary, oversight commissions, the free press, and opposition parties. The more Hindus

who embrace his ideology, the more popular Modi becomes, giving him political cover to launch attacks on judges, bureaucrats, and journalists. The more control he has over India's government and press, the easier it will be for him to spread Hindutva propaganda (Vaishnav, 2019).

Prior to Modi's rise, the BJP's electoral success was hampered by an elite base that supported the party's economic and social reforms. Many upper-caste Indians were deeply concerned about a long-running effort to expand India's caste-based affirmative action program for university admissions and government jobs, viewing the BJP as a party that would oppose this and other attempts to undermine the caste hierarchy. Under Modi, the party has been able to significantly expand its demographic base among both lower-caste and poor Hindus (two groups that overlap to some extent but not completely) while maintaining its core. By 2019, poor Hindu voters were just as likely as rich Hindu voters to support the BJP (Basu, 2018a).

Research Methodology

In the field of political science, researchers commonly embrace one of two major methodological stances: the qualitative and quantitative method (McNabb, 2015). This research is based on a qualitative method. This study is based on Historical research to investigate the reasons for the rise of ethnic democracy in India and understand how Modi's eight-year rule increased tension between religious groups, leading to sectarian wars.

Secondary sources were primarily used in the thesis. The current study material was developed after consulting a number of books, newspapers, magazines, and journals, as well as after visiting seminars and speaking with democracy specialists. The following research design describes the features of this methodological framework.

Research Design

This research will utilize the Historical research design to document an important event. With this approach, a comprehensive description of the incident will be provided for possible use by academics, decision-makers, and the general public (Halperin & Heath, 2020). This kind of study

may inspire additional research, and the results may be used to evaluate existing theories.

The historical research approach offers a number of advantages. The first benefit of employing historical research is the ability to create or derive a solid theory by a more in-depth examination of specific cases of behavior and occurrence. By referencing the past, the historical approach helps to make sense of the present.

The second benefit is that historical occurrences can provide information about upcoming ones; for instance, data from previous advertising campaigns can be examined to help with the development of new ones. Utilizing historical information to inform the present and future is the fundamental idea. It requires a lot of skill. To identify trends and variations, the data must be analyzed. Based on the facts, the most logical theories and ideas must be developed and backed up by data.

By conducting historical studies, the historical research method offers researchers a better understanding of why something occurred and its effects, which is its third advantage (Nwolise, 2011). Researchers can use this data to make predictions about the future or gain a deeper understanding of the past.

The ability to evaluate an event in greater detail, which can aid in decision-making, is the fourth benefit of historical research. It can be applied to decision-making in a range of fields, such as law, business, public policy, and education. Comprehending the historical context of current circumstances may enable us to make better-informed decisions about how to handle them.

The preservation of cultural heritage is the fifth benefit of historical research. Historical research can record and preserve cultural history, including customs and traditions (Rowlinson, 2005). It is possible to work toward preserving these cultural aspects for future generations when one is aware of their historical significance.

Last but not least, studying the past piques one's curiosity and encourages critical thought. A more critical and introspective approach to comprehending history and its applicability to the present can be developed by investigating different historical viewpoints and interpretations.

Data Analysis

In this research paper, explanatory data analysis will be used to analyze the data. When there is limited information, explanatory research is a research method that looks into why something happens (Buchanan et al., 2013). A "cause and effect" model can also be used to describe explanatory research, which looks for previously undiscovered patterns and trends in the data. It is frequently regarded as a kind of causal research because of this.

Among the most popular research techniques are the following:

- Observations
- Literature reviews
- Experiments
- Pilot studies
- Interviews and focus groups

The method selected is determined by a number of factors, such as the question's structure, budget, and timeline. A literature review is an excellent research method to start if there has already been some research on the subject. In this study, explanatory data analysis will be used to analyze the data through a literature review on the main factors and reasons that at 75, India world's largest democracy, has been turned into turmoil and the impact of RSS on policy formulation in India. The focus was how the policies of Narendra caused of deteriorated conditions of democracy in India. Through explanatory analysis, the researcher will attempt to discover the truth about the sector's biggest democracy as claimed by India. There is an influence of Hindu ideology, and they encourage Hindu nationalism and violate the basic rights of minorities, specifically Muslims.

Theoretical Framework

In political science, critical theory is a method of understanding politics that challenges existing conventions and perspectives. Its ultimate goal is to create a more just and equal society. According to critical thinkers, the current social order contains numerous injustices and inequalities. They aim to identify these problems and develop remedies (Devetak, 2013). In other words, critical theory seeks to better society. The Frankfurt School,

a collection of early twentieth-century German academics, is credited with helping to shape critical theory. Since then, critical theory has evolved and been applied in a variety of ways by scholars from other fields. A "Critical Theory," according to Frankfurt School thinkers, differs from a "traditional" theory in that it has a clear practical objective, such as gaining a knowledge of the universe that leads to human "emancipation from slavery."

Critical Theory examines the concept of "true democracy" as follows:

The early stages of Critical Theory sought to distinguish the concept of "real democracy" from the systems of government then common in Western societies. According to critical theorists, true democracy is reasonable because it allows individuals to have control over the social processes that affect them and their life choices.

The next phases of Critical Theory were dominated by anti-democratic forces, such as the advent of fascism in the 1930s. These studies focused on fascist states and authoritarian individuals (Nickerson, 2022).

The lens of Critical Theory is being utilized in this research to answer all of the research questions related to the rise of ethnic democracy in India, i.e. Impact of RSS on policy formulation. India, once claimed as the world's largest democracy, today is in serious crisis under Prime Minister Narendra. During Modi's eight-year rule, tension increased between religious groups and led to serious consequences, such as sectarian wars and slaughter.

MODI'S AUTHORITARIANISM: THE RISE OF RADICAL DEMOCRACY

At 75, India's Deteriorated Democracy

India became the first democracy in South Asia after becoming a British colony, and it has since transformed from a poor country into one of the fastest-growing economies, earning a place at the top table of international affairs and serving as a democratic counterweight to its authoritarian neighbor, China. However, experts and opponents claim that since Modi took office in 2014, the nation has been accelerating its reverting from some

commitments. They charge that his populist administration is preoccupied with advancing a Hindu nationalist agenda and abusing its unchecked political power to destroy democratic liberties.

The protests by India's main opposition Congress party on August 5, 2022, against shooting up food prices and unemployment, started out like any other objection in recent protests: an electorally weakened opposition marching to the streets of New Delhi to criticize Prime Minister Narendra Modi's enormously popular administration (Saaliq, 2022). The primary challenger to Modi in the last two general elections, Rahul Gandhi, led important Congress MPs to the Parliament, which swiftly changed the course of the protests and resulted in violent standoffs with police.

Gandhi later tweeted, "Democracy is a memory (in India)." The administration ridiculed Gandhi's comment, which was mainly considered as just another desperate attempt by a troubled opposition party to maintain its standing. But it raised concerns that India's democracy, the biggest in the world with close to 1.4 billion citizens, is declining and its democratic foundations are crumbling. Trust in the judiciary as a check on executive power, according to experts, is deteriorating. Attacks on the media and free expression have become more obvious. Hindu nationalists are increasingly attacking religious minorities. Additionally, internet crackdowns and the detention of activists have put an end to largely peaceful protests, sometimes against provocative policies.

Profiling Modi's policies 2019

Since the start of his second term as Prime Minister of India in 2019, Narendra Modi has pursued policies that have weakened democracy. His administration has manipulated the law to crush dissent, abused the investigative process to pursue flimsy charges against political opponents. The Indian democracy is suffering a sharp collapse on a number of fronts.

This process was expedited by the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP), a Hindu nationalist party in power, which won a resounding victory in the most recent national elections (Ganguly, 2021).

The decision to revoke the special status of Indian-administrated Kashmir in August 2019 did not follow constitutional procedure, and the Citizenship Amendment Act, which was passed in December 2019, benefited neighboring countries' religious minorities but excluded Muslims despite the fact that many of their sects face repression in Afghanistan and Pakistan. It includes clauses that let the state label someone a terrorist without giving supporting evidence, among other things. The Central Bureau of Investigation and the Directorate of Enforcement, two of India's top investigative organizations, are allegedly involved in settling political grudges, according to some opposition lawmakers.

RSS

Gandhi was the first victim of the Hindutva ideology that has plagued India since its freedom. Gandhi and all the communities that supported secularism suffered terrible repercussions. Since then, every right-wing political organization in India, including the RSS, Shiv Sena, Hindu Mahasbha, and most recently the BJP, led by Narendra Modi, the most ignorant, fascist, cruel, and extreme person in South Asia, has been built on the Hindutva ideology (Singh, 2023).

Modi was a member of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangha before joining politics; this organization has strong ties to Hindu nationalism and views India as the holiest country for Hindus. The troubles of religious minorities have been worse since he took office. The number of mosques and churches being attacked has increased, according to organizations in India that support minority rights, and Muslims and Christians are no longer permitted to observe their religious rites.

Christians have experienced a particularly violent year in 2021, with 500 new attacks reported, an increase of 80%. Cow slaughter and beef sales are illegal in some Indian states, and offenders are subject to harsh penalties. On April 14, a group of radical Hindus broke into a church and detained everyone inside. The Indian government hasn't done anything to manage the situation and frequently participates in it.

Numerous Hindus back Modi because of his nationalist ideologies, which allow him to more

quickly put his racist policies into action. Due to this, he was able to easily win the 2019 elections.

Modi consistently depicts India as having previously been a beautiful Hindu culture that was destroyed by the Mughals and, subsequently, the British Empire. According to the BJP, Hindus were forcibly converted to other religions against their choice, and it is the leadership's duty to use all available measures to undo those conversions under the direction of Modi, known as the "Butcher of Gujrat."

Similarly to this, since independence, the Sikh Community has also been targeted by Hindutva ideology. The Sikhs are now on the receiving end of Hindutva's sharpened swords as a result of their growing call for a separate state, Khalistan. Most recently, on May 29, 2022, the most famous Punjabi musician, Shubhdeep Singh Sidhu. People who have experienced discrimination have also charged the government with neglecting its responsibilities, failing to protect minorities, and failing to uphold the law (Jaffrelot & Schoch, 2021).

Modi, Authoritarianism

Hindus, who make up the majority of India's population, are currently quite fond of Modi. Some people even regard him as a god, believing him to be the Hindu people's savior. Numerous academics think Modi is a populist leader who has impacted India with his stirring speeches. He has restricted free press since 2014 and uses the media to spread his propaganda, which makes him an authoritarian as well (Mowlavi, 2023). Since Modi hasn't held any press conferences with journalists, many of them have decided to support him and his administration out of fear of going to jail. Since the media is now a tool of government propaganda due to high taxes, whatever Modi says must be put into action immediately and without hesitation. Despite the customary prohibition against civil servants belonging to political parties, this has led to an increase in party workers since 2014.

The Central Bureau of Investigation has reportedly detained and questioned 95% of Indian politicians since 2014, and many of them have joined the BJP in an effort to have their cases dropped, according to reporting from The Indian Express. It is challenging for courts to independently examine

and pursue cases in India since the judicial system is no longer as independent as it once was and is heavily affected by the executive branch. Indian courts frequently hesitate to register lawsuits or postpone proceedings as a result (Patel, 2022).

Conclusion

Democracy is not founded on genetic differences between individuals. It was something that needed daily consumption and use. When their British rulers created a threat to their history and culture after dominance, the Indians began to explore democracy. They agree that democracy made the British people great, and from 1857 to 1947, their descendants were taught democracy and all of its intricacies. India's politics had degenerated into immorality, and democracy had not developed as it ought to have.

India is no longer a secular state, and the Hindutva movement has further divided the already-fractured nation. Not only are minorities living in India threatened by the BJP's annexation and expansion policies, but the neighboring nations are also concerned. In terms of crimes and cruelty towards minorities, the BJP dictatorship has far outdone the British, and its control has consistently upheld the hard-liner Hindutva ideology. Because of the close ties between the military and the economy, the military arm of the RSS and Shiv Sena is more powerful than ever. Despite this, world powers have not taken any action against them.

The largest democracy in the world is currently burning itself out at a far faster rate. India's society has been extremely divided during Modi's eight years in power, which may threaten the semi-democratic structure of the nation. Serious consequences, including sectarian conflicts and killing, could result from the rising hostility between the various religious groups. Radical Islamic organizations have grown and attracted new members as a result of discrimination against Muslims in India. Modi might pose a serious threat to the biggest democracy in the world if he is not forced out of office like the others.

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